

Ocean Size

Naomie S. Baguinat

Assistant Professor IV
Jose Rizal Memorial State University

In you, I found a treasure I could not find in the entire universe.
You are the apple of my eye, yet I fear you might go away one day.
 Will the next day find no one beside me?
 I fear that you could be gone tomorrow in a blink.
 I fear that one day, in broad daylight, you'll walk away
That one day, before I open my eyes, you will be behind that door,
And the next morning I will wake up and find myself without you near me.

In you, I found my only hope, the angel of my dreams.
 You've brought out all the strength in me;
With you, I defeated the darkest shadows of my days.
 You've given me a thousand occasions to celebrate.
Then one day, from behind the clouds, a white light appears,
 The darkness fades, and when I open my eyes,
 I see the sincerest love that is setting me free.

My every fear went away with the dark gray sky;
It happens when I know that I have you here with me.
 You turn my whole world upside down,
 And even when everything changes back to gray,
I once again say that whatever may come, well, come what may
For I see your promise when you look me in the eyes.

I thank you for loving me.
 I thank you for gracing me with all of your patience,
 For loving me even when I am the worst on this planet.
I thank you for taking all my pains and putting them on your shoulders,
For accepting me with all your heart, with nothing else to gain.
 I thank you for making me feel that I am not alone.

I will always trust you wherever you lead me.
I will always follow you, even if I cannot see where to go.
 If you ever think one day that I would go away,
 Don't be afraid, as I promise I won't walk away.
 I need you in my future so we can be together;
 Though storms may come as we go along,
We will achieve our dreams together and always hold still.

I will stand by your side and fulfill my promise.
We will run towards our dreams and move forward in life.
One day the weather may change from windy, to rainy, to stormy,
But we will hold on together towards a beautiful sunny day,
 And survive the storm hands clasped, fingers crossed,
Holding on to the promises we made to make it through.

We fight our battles as one and deal with the struggles;
We can do it because I found a faithful partner in you.
And we both will never be alone through the highs and lows.
 With you, I can always thank God for giving me you.
 I love you, my home.

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